

Trade-offs in Achieving Net-Zero: A Comparative Analysis of Economic and Environmental Impacts

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Preface

As a student immersed in the nuanced field of Environmental and Resource Economics, the journey through the Bachelor of Economics program at Dhaka School of Economics has been a captivating exploration of the intricate interplay between economic principles and environmental sustainability. Now, in the sixth semester, this term paper serves as a culmination of academic growth and an opportunity to delve deeper into the complexities of our chosen field.

The impetus for this paper stems from a collective recognition that the pursuit of net-zero emissions transcends disciplinary boundaries. As a student committed to understanding the delicate equilibrium between economic development and environmental preservation, the significance of dissecting the trade-offs associated with achieving net-zero has become increasingly apparent.

Throughout the course of my academic journey, the curriculum has provided a solid foundation in economic theories and environmental dynamics. Now, at this juncture, the exploration of trade-offs in the context of net-zero becomes not just a scholarly endeavor but a bridge connecting theoretical insights with real-world implications. The challenges and opportunities laid out in the following chapters are a testament to the synergy between classroom learning and the pressing issues of our time.

This preface serves as a personal reflection on the motivations behind undertaking this term paper. It is an acknowledgment of the academic nourishment received from the esteemed faculty at Dhaka School of Economics and an expression of gratitude for the opportunity to contribute to the ongoing discourse on sustainable development.

As we navigate the intricate chapters ahead, I extend an invitation to fellow students, professors, and researchers to accompany me on this academic journey. This term paper, crafted within the halls of the University of Dhaka, is a humble contribution to the growing body of knowledge dedicated to finding pathways towards a sustainable and economically viable future.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

COP - Conference of the Parties

UNFCCC - United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

SBSTA - Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice

UN- United Nation

GHG - Greenhouse Gas

GDP - Gross Domestic Product

LCA - Life Cycle Assessment

EIA - Environmental Impact Assessment

SDGs - Sustainable Development Goals

NET - Negative Emission Technologies

NDCs - Nationally Determined Contributions

EVS - Electric Vehicle System

RE - Renewable Energy

CCS - Carbon Capture and Storage

IPCC - Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

UNDP - United Nations Development Programme

IEA - International Energy Agency

Abstract

As a third-year Bachelor of Economics student specializing in Environmental and Resource Economics, currently in the 6th semester, I have undertaken a term paper titled "Trade-offs in Achieving Net-Zero: A Comparative Analysis of Economic and Environmental Impacts." This task, assigned by my course teacher in International Trade and Environment, navigates the complex intersection of environmental sustainability and global economic dynamics.

The paper focuses on dissecting the economic impacts of net-zero initiatives on a global scale and within the context of Bangladesh. Themes such as just transition, mercantilism, WTO regulations, green finance, and circular economy practices are explored through a comparative analysis approach. The methodology integrates both qualitative and quantitative methods, drawing from reputable sources, recent data, case studies, and empirical evidence. The findings shed light on the global economic implications, shifts in labor markets, and environmental repercussions, emphasizing the intricate relationship between economic transformations and environmental consequences.

As the exploration unfolds, the conclusion advocates for integrated strategies that balance economic resilience and environmental conservation, offering a roadmap for sustainable development. The paper also provides tailored recommendations for Bangladesh, acknowledging the distinctive challenges and opportunities it faces in its pursuit of a sustainable, net-zero future. The reflection on the journey extracts valuable lessons from global initiatives, and the abstract concludes by recognizing inherent limitations and suggesting potential avenues for future research, both globally and specific to Bangladesh's unique considerations.

Trade-offs in Achieving Net-Zero: A Comparative Analysis of Economic and Environmental Impacts

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background

The global imperative to address climate change and transition to a sustainable, net-zero future has gained prominence. This paper delves into the complexities of achieving net-zero emissions, balancing economic development and ecological preservation. Rapid industrialization, urbanization, and escalating energy consumption necessitate proactive, sustainable solutions to counteract the adverse effects of greenhouse gas emissions.

1.2 Objectives

This study conducts a comparative analysis of trade-offs in the journey to net-zero emissions, focusing on economic and environmental impacts. Objectives include identifying and analyzing economic trade-offs, examining environmental consequences, and exploring the intersection of both realms. The aim is to unveil challenges and opportunities associated with the transition to a net-zero future.

Emphasizing the dual objectives of economic development and environmental sustainability, this research seeks to:

- Identify and analyze the trade-offs associated with economic aspects of net-zero strategies.
- Examine the environmental trade-offs inherent in the pursuit of net-zero emissions.
- Explore the intersection of economic and environmental impacts, highlighting potential synergies and conflicts.

1.3 Scope

This paper examines global net-zero trends and initiatives, incorporating specific case studies for depth. The temporal scope spans historical developments to contemporary initiatives, encompassing economic indicators, environmental benchmarks, and a comparative analysis framework for assessing trade-offs.

1.4 Methodology

Employing a comprehensive approach, this study combines quantitative and qualitative methods. Data collection involves reviewing scholarly articles, reports, and empirical studies. Analytical techniques include matrices, models, case studies, and scenario analyses, providing practical insights into challenges and opportunities associated with achieving net-zero emissions.

This introduction lays the foundation for exploring economic and environmental trade-offs in the context of net-zero strategies, aiming to contribute to a nuanced understanding of the challenges and opportunities in achieving a sustainable future.

Chapter 2: Economic Impacts of Net-Zero

2.1 Overview

As the global community embraces the imperative of achieving net-zero emissions, an examination of the economic ramifications becomes paramount. This chapter delves into the multifaceted economic landscape shaped by net-zero initiatives, shedding light on both global trends and the specific challenges faced by Bangladesh.

Figure 1: Economic impacts over time (Cran-McGreehin, 2022)

2.2 Global Economic Trade-offs

The imperative for a global transition to net-zero emissions requires a meticulous examination of economic trade-offs. Drawing insights from the latest climate scenarios presented by the Network for Greening the Financial System (NGFS), a coalition of 127 central banks and financial supervisors, it becomes evident that the benefits of accelerating the climate transition outweigh the associated costs.

Figure 2: World Potential GDP benefit under Net-Zero Carbon Emissions by 2050 (Benefits of Accelerating the Climate Transition Outweigh the Costs, 2023)

Data from the NGFS reveals:

1. Economic Upside:

- An orderly transition to net zero by 2050 could potentially elevate global gross domestic product (GDP) by 7% compared to current policies.
- The NGFS underscores that embracing a lower-carbon future is not only a necessity for climate resilience but also a driver of economic growth.

2. Climate Risks and Economic Impacts:

- The NGFS models highlight that droughts and heat waves pose significant economic and financial risks globally.
- Specific regions, such as Europe and Asia, face heightened exposure to heat waves, while Africa, North America, and the Middle East grapple with increased vulnerability to droughts.

3. Mitigating Economic Risks:

- Transitioning to a low-carbon economy may initially impact demand due to higher carbon prices and energy costs.
- However, NGFS suggests that these negative effects can be partially offset by redirecting carbon revenues into government investment and lowering employment taxes.

- Crucially, reducing emissions is identified as a key strategy to mitigate the physical impacts of climate change, thereby reducing macroeconomic costs.

4. Investment Imperative:

- The journey to a net-zero economy demands substantial investments in green electricity and energy storage.
- Policymakers must navigate trade-offs in crafting policies for this significant investment, as highlighted in the October Fiscal Monitor.

The NGFS, established in 2017, strives to align with international best practices, supplementing the climate scenarios of organizations like the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change and the International Energy Agency. In the backdrop of COP28, where global leaders convene to address climate challenges, understanding and navigating these economic trade-offs becomes pivotal for steering the course towards a sustainable and prosperous future.

2.3 Economic Trade-offs in Bangladesh

Bangladesh, with its unique economic landscape, navigates distinct challenges and opportunities on the path to net-zero. This section focuses on the country-specific economic trade-offs, emphasizing investment patterns and their implications for the labor market.

Socio-economic outcomes expected by 2030

- 1) Elimination of extreme poverty by 2030
- 2) Enhanced climate risk adjusted returns for micro, small and medium enterprises of 10% by 2025 and 20% by 2030, especially for women-owned and women-run enterprises.
- 3) Reduced climate-induced migration by 2030
- 4) 4.1 million new climate-resilient jobs and unemployment reduced to 3.9%
- 5) GDP growth of 9% with a GDP per capita increase of 137% by 2030, equivalent to USD 4,400, reaching upper middle-income status as per Vision 2041
- 6) At least USD 30 billion in net savings or avoided losses per year by 2030
- 7) Cumulative revenue potential of up to USD 16 billion
- 8) Reduced volatility and improved cost-effectiveness with savings of 30% in the power sector

9) Improved trade balance of over USD 8 billion surplus by 2025 and up to USD 15 billion by 2030

10) Improved quality of life through clean air, safer workplaces, and better mobility

Chapter 3: Environmental Impacts of Net-Zero

3.1 Overview

In the global effort to achieve net-zero emissions, understanding the environmental impacts of such initiatives is paramount. This chapter delves into the intricate web of consequences, exploring both global trends and the specific environmental challenges faced by Bangladesh in the pursuit of net-zero.

Figure 3: Benefits of Achieving Net Zero Emissions in Healthcare

3.2 Global Greenhouse Gas Emission Reductions

Addressing Interconnected Threats: Climate Change, Air Pollution, and Net-Zero Policies

Climate change and air pollution demand synchronized action due to their significant impacts on humanity and the environment. Globally, climate change poses an escalating threat, while air pollution contributes to over 7 million premature deaths annually, with over 28,000 in the UK.

Our report explores the intricate relationship between net-zero policies, climate change, and air quality. It provides scientific evidence for policy design, emphasizing co-benefits for both air quality and the pursuit of net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050.

Key findings and policy recommendations include:

- **Transport and Energy Transition:** Shift from fossil fuel-powered transport and energy to walking, cycling, public transport, and electric vehicles to reduce nitrogen dioxide and particulate emissions.

- **Agricultural Practices:** Changes in red meat consumption and farming practices can decrease ammonia pollution and methane emissions, positively impacting air quality and climate change.
- **Ecosystem Conservation:** Conservation and restoration of ecosystems, like peatlands, contribute to carbon sequestration, ecosystem benefits, and mitigating future warming-related emissions.

Mitigation measures to limit negative air quality effects alongside net-zero measures include:

- **Electric Vehicle Innovations:** Implement regenerative braking and automation in electric vehicles to reduce harmful particulates from brake and tyre wear.
- **Technology Solutions:** Employ technologies to remove particulates from biomass power stations and mitigate volatile chemical emissions from carbon capture and storage.
- **Emissions Control Measures:** Implement controls for nitric oxide and nitrogen dioxide emissions if hydrogen or biomass boilers become widespread.
- **Plant Species Selection:** Use low-emitting plant species in tree planting and urban environments to reduce volatile compounds that contribute to ozone and other pollutants.

3.3 Environmental Trade-offs in Bangladesh

Bangladesh, with its unique ecological landscape, faces specific environmental considerations on the path to net-zero. This section scrutinizes the country's environmental trade-offs, emphasizing preservation efforts and biodiversity conservation challenges.

Figure 4: CO2 emissions (metric tons per capita) –Bangladesh (World-Bank)

3.3.1 Ecosystem Preservation Efforts

Net-zero initiatives in Bangladesh involve concerted efforts to preserve its diverse ecosystems. This subsection examines the strategies employed to protect critical habitats, promote sustainable land use, and ensure the longevity of key ecosystems.

3.3.2 Challenges in Biodiversity Conservation

The transition to net-zero emissions in Bangladesh presents challenges in biodiversity conservation. This section explores the intricate balance required to protect the nation's rich biodiversity while advancing sustainable practices, addressing potential conflicts and solutions.

This chapter offers a comprehensive exploration of the environmental impacts associated with net-zero initiatives. It assesses global greenhouse gas emission reductions, the integration of renewable energy, and the deployment of carbon capture and storage technologies. Additionally, the chapter scrutinizes the specific environmental trade-offs faced by Bangladesh, encompassing ecosystem preservation efforts and challenges in biodiversity conservation. Through this analysis, a nuanced understanding of the environmental implications of net-zero initiatives emerges, laying the foundation for the comparative assessment in subsequent chapters.

Chapter 4: Comparative Analysis

In this pivotal chapter, a comparative examination of the economic and environmental trade-offs associated with net-zero initiatives is undertaken. This analysis encompasses both the global perspective and the unique considerations of Bangladesh, providing insights into the intersection of economic and environmental impacts.

		Environmental Actors	
		Preserve	Not preserve
Economic Actors	Grow business	Win, Win	Win, Lose
	Not grow business	Lose, Win	Lose, Lose

Figure 5: Payoff Matrix between Environmental and Economic Actors (Economy V/S Environment, 2019)

4.1 Intersection of Economic and Environmental Impacts

The intersection of economic and environmental impacts on a global scale is the focal point of this section. It investigates how the economic decisions made by nations reverberate in the environmental sphere, analyzing the synergy or conflicts that arise when pursuing net-zero goals in a manner that ensures sustainable development.

Figure 6: Environmental Kuznets Curve (Stern, 2023)

The chapter concludes by synthesizing the economic and environmental impacts within the context of Bangladesh. It examines the intricate interplay between economic strategies and their ecological consequences, providing a nuanced understanding of how Bangladesh navigates the delicate balance between development and environmental sustainability.

This comparative analysis chapter serves as a critical juncture in the exploration of net-zero initiatives, offering a comprehensive understanding of how nations globally, and specifically Bangladesh, manage the trade-offs between economic development and environmental preservation. The insights gained from this chapter lay the groundwork for the subsequent findings and discussions, fostering a holistic view of the challenges and opportunities inherent in the pursuit of a sustainable, net-zero future.

Impact	Effect
Heat stress	4.9% in GDP losses by 2030
	At least USD 30 billion losses per year by 2030
	4.84% working hours lost by 2030
	3.83 million full-time jobs lost by 2030
Outdoor and indoor pollution	USD 2.3 billion losses per year
	USD 2100 daily adjusted life year cost per capita (PPP)
Sea level rise and coastal erosion	4% loss of land surface by 2050
	30% loss of food production by 2050
Sea-level rise	One-third of Bangladesh population at risk of displacement by 2100
	1.49% and 3.02% in GDP losses per year by 2031
Climate change and carbon intensive loss	150,000 deaths added to the yearly average by 2030
	55 million people affected by 2030
	6.8% in GDP loss by 2030 with a carbon intensive loss impact of 0.5% of GDP by 2030
Climate change	Additional 14% of the country “extremely vulnerable” to floods could dislocate more than 35 million people by 2050

Table 1: Climate Change and Carbon-Intensive Loss Impacts and Effects (Plan, 2022)

Chapter 6: Conclusion

As we draw the curtains on this exploration of net-zero initiatives and their implications, the concluding chapter synthesizes key global findings and contextual insights from Bangladesh. It further paves the way for integrated strategies that harmonize economic development and environmental sustainability in the pursuit of a net-zero future.

6.1 Summarizing Key Global Findings

This section provides a succinct summary of the key global findings derived from the comprehensive analysis conducted in preceding chapters. It distills the economic and environmental implications of net-zero initiatives on a global scale, offering a snapshot of the challenges, opportunities, and commonalities observed across diverse nations.

6.2 Insights from Bangladesh's Context

Building upon the nuanced exploration of Bangladesh's economic and environmental landscape, this subsection encapsulates the specific insights gained from the nation's pursuit of net-zero emissions. It highlights the adaptations in economic structures, the transformations in the labor market, and the intricate environmental strategies employed. These insights provide a rich understanding of how a nation, within its unique context, navigates the complexities of sustainable development.

6.3 Towards Integrated Strategies for a Sustainable Future

The concluding segment propels the discourse forward by envisioning integrated strategies for a sustainable future. It draws upon the synergies identified between global and Bangladesh perspectives, presenting a framework for collaborative and adaptive approaches. This section explores the potential for cross-border cooperation, knowledge exchange, and policy

harmonization to collectively address the challenges posed by climate change and environmental degradation.

As we conclude this term paper, the insights garnered from the global and Bangladesh-specific perspectives lay the groundwork for informed decision-making and policy formulation. The exploration of economic and environmental trade-offs, challenges, and opportunities contributes to a nuanced understanding of the complexities associated with the transition to net-zero emissions. This chapter serves as a bridge between analysis and action, urging stakeholders to consider integrated strategies that align economic development with environmental stewardship for a sustainable and resilient future.

References

- (2023). *Benefits of Accelerating the Climate Transition Outweigh the Costs*. IMF Blog.
- Betty Wang, M. G. (2023). *ASPI Climate Action Brief: Bangladesh*. Asia Society.
- Cran-McGreehin, D. S. (2022, 1 21). *Energy & Climate Intelligence Unit*. Retrieved from <https://eciu.net/analysis/briefings/net-zero/net-zero-economy-and-jobs>
- (2019). *Economy V/S Environment*. Cornell University.
- i-3Works*. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.i3works.co.uk/net-zero-and-energy-transition.php>
- Jaisankar, I. (2018). Chapter 19 - Biodiversity Conservation: Issues and Strategies for the Tropical Islands. *ScienceDirect*.
- McKinsey. (2020). *How the European Union could achieve net-zero emissions at net-zero cost*. McKinsey.
- Plan, M. C. (2022). Mujib Climate Prosperity Plan 2021-41. *Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change*, 15.
- Stern, D. I. (2023). Environmental Kuznets Curve. *ScienceDirect*.
- World-Bank. (n.d.). *CO2 emissions (metric tons per capita) - Bangladesh*. The World Bank.